

QUALITY AND SKILL-BASED ASSESSMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

One of the most important components of instructional programs is evaluation, which indicates an actual dedication to the execution and involvement of the educational system. As an educational assessment tool, we must keep in mind that various assessments are appropriate for different learning requirements and student capacities. No evaluation is without restrictions, and its advantages include validity, reliability, and objectivity. It is the result of the pupils' performance and accomplishments. Students' work performance varies according on their excitement, motivation, competence, and ability. The selection of assessment is critical for increasing the desire of learners to finish the task and for teachers to decide if it previously represented their goals or not. Instructors must be creative, attractive, and creative in managing student assessments. Educators must be creative, engaging, and inventive in managing assessment tasks so that students are excited and interested in undertaking all sorts of exams, including traditional ones. Whatever form of evaluation is used, the purpose of implementation is to deliver direct benefit to students. All kinds of assessments, including projects, portfolios, and others, serve to fulfill the fundamental objective of evaluating and triggering student achievement and making visible progress.

KEY WORDS

assessment, development, progress, achievement, instruction, competence, acquire

“The ability to understand the different purposes and types of assessment in order to select the most appropriate type of assessment is to meet a specific purpose”.

Larry Ainsworth

Introduction

Since assessment is a vital component of the educational process, it has a long history. According to research, the first assessment was used in China. The evaluation was known as the "Chinese Imperial Examinations" when it first took place in this country in 587. It was essential to pass an exam in order to work here as a state servant. These oral and then written examinations were held in China until 1905. They pondered about ways to test pupils' knowledge and experimented with various approaches since the early days of education in Europe. Exams were previously administered orally.

Students responded to the questions in Latin, and the teacher graded them. The first written exams were given at Cambridge University in 1792.

The evaluation history is divided into many stages by pedagogical researchers. Prior to the First World War, students' knowledge was tested by exams, with a focus on understanding the substance of the disciplines.

As the growth tendencies in the area of education increased in the early twentieth century, new concepts surrounding the assessment of student achievements emerged. The "idea of progressive education" was born in the United States during this time period and eventually expanded to other nations.

The essence of the "idea of progressive education" was that education was aimed at developing life skills that corresponded to the directions of growth of industry and technology rather than scientific knowledge. Such fresh perspectives on educational material gradually altered the method to evaluation. Assessment was now more focused on applying knowledge and relating it to real-world scenarios.

However, by the 1950s and 1960s of the twentieth century, this concept had lost its importance.

Since the dawn of the space era, the educational requirements of the major countries have shifted, and approaches to student evaluation have begun to evolve in a new direction. For example, the United States was concerned by the Soviet Union's advances in science (conquest of space, etc.) and focused on the teaching of exact sciences and their more effective assessment. In the following decades, stronger evaluation standards were established in conformity with the nature of education. As a result, students were required to answer various levels of questions within a certain time constraint in order to exhibit their problem-solving abilities. These sorts of questions can be used to assess a student's specific knowledge and abilities, as well as their mastery. Later, specialists began to consider specific programs that would allow these comparisons across schools, regions, and states by removing them from the classroom level. This demonstrates that testing and enhancing assessment processes continue to be ongoing and permanent.

Main Part

Assessment is an inevitable and crucial part of teaching and learning, generally education system, therefore it defines whether or not education goals are met and it is the way to measure learners' success. It has effects on decisions about grades, placement, needs, curriculum, and, in some cases, it shapes the future. During the process of gathering the data for effective planning, evidence and instruction some words like measurement, assessment and evaluation are irreplaceable simultaneously are used interchangeable while having crucially different meanings.

Measurement does not have any other meaning as it applies in education and it simply means defining, determining the characteristics, attributes and dimensions of the focused skill, field of science, knowledge or any other object. Consequently, measurement of knowledge can give reliable results when used properly, precisely for collecting data. They might be standard scores or percentages.

Assessment can be accepted one of the basic and significant measurement tools in education. Educators collect data by conducting interviews, surveys, monitoring and observing behavior and at the same time by giving tests and questionnaires. It should be reliable and valid to be used in measuring the learner's knowledge. In evaluation creating or making valid and reliable assessments, tests or exams is critical to precisely measuring educational data. Evaluating the data collected however, is equally significant to the affordable use of the information for instruction. In education, evaluation is the process of using the information gathered in the assessments.

Teachers use this information to judge the relationship between what was intended by the instruction and what was learned. It is crucial to evaluate the information gathered to define what learners know and understand, how far they have progressed and how fast, and how their scores and progress compare to those of other students. Therefore, assessments should be chosen attentively and precisely which make them quality assessments.

Quality assessment assists to determine the student success and make a map of learning journey which leads to achievements and get outstanding results. It focuses on the targeted areas of subjects with complete precision. Assessment in education in order to be a quality assessment should have several criteria and characteristics such as:

- Content validity: The exam should be accurately and highly organized and ready to measure and assess learning.
- Reliability: the test should be referenced.
- Generating interest by the student: The reason why assessments should be objective in nature is gaining the student's interest. Subjectively long tests in nature do not even gain the learner's attention, therefore it is waste of time and boring to be done. Due to the fact that they should be explicit, creative, attention-grabbing which does not give any sense of boredom to the candidates.
- Consequential relevance: Conducting an exam, test or assessment requires much time, dedication, and plenty of resources; nobody would want that much of complicated and hard work to go in vain and the result of the assessment should be so exact so that it can be used as a tool or as an evidence to compare, measure and analyze the data for next reference of the student's performance.

The idea that evaluations must be carried out in a limited setting and require paper-based testing has existed for decades in our society. However, on the path of advancement technology has advanced to the point that it is currently influencing every industry, including education. The idea that education is obsolete can be dispelled with the use of modern online evaluation technologies.

Now, let's delve deeply into how online evaluations are categorized:

- Regardless of the location or time, you can give the test to a lot of people.

An internet-based test is not restricted by logistics or infrastructure. Depending on the amount of time available, you may carry out it on as many applicants as you like, who are going to be attending from their own locations.

- Using unpredictability in both the questions and the answers is the best approach to prevent cheating.

The characteristic of randomizing is mainly found throughout the online quiz creator program.

This function creates a unique quiz for each candidate by selecting questions at unique and organizing their specific answers in an order determined by chance. This assures cheat protection.

- No requirement for an assessor.

Although tests taken online are virtual in nature, they are carried out through technology and don't need to be supervised.

- Instant utilization of records

Throughout the testing of the applicants, the system records the data in an organized manner that is readily available for later use. There is no shortage of online quiz creator software accessible in the digital education industry.

Quality evaluation techniques are widely accessible due to the significant advancements in the field of education. Whichever option you choose now will depend on your needs and preferences. It is now your turn to take advantage of the plethora of assessment options available in the educational online market, which can meet everyone's needs.

It is a good idea to use the Bloom's Taxonomy system to create assessments in the classroom that help students improve their critical thinking abilities.

Benjamin Bloom led a team of educational psychologists who discovered in 1956 that over 95% of test questions only asked students to recall facts. In response, Bloom created a classification system for critical thinking behaviors in education. These six stages begin with fact recall and progress to evaluation via progressively more intricate and abstract levels. A fresh group of cognitive psychologists led by former Bloom student Lorin Anderson revised the taxonomy in the 1990s to reflect 21st century work.

A well-crafted question will flow between all levels. These are what really bloom skill-based education:

Recalling: The ability to retrieve or retain knowledge

Understanding: To elucidate notions or principles

Applying: Making new use of previously acquired information, a guideline, or a **technique**

Analyzing: Dividing data into constituent parts in order to investigate connections and understandings

Assessing: Determining the worth of information or concepts in order to support a stance, viewpoint, or choice.

Creating: To combine concepts in novel ways to produce a new good or viewpoint.

All online or in-person assessments adhere to the concepts of Bloom's taxonomy.

Bloom's Taxonomy	Methods of online assessment
Knowledge	Multiple-choice, true/false, gap filling and games
Perception	Simulations and animations
Application	Case method, essay, and short responses
Analyze, synthesize, and evaluate	Essays, projects, presentations, portfolios, virtual labs, and so on.

The following areas, according to K. Morgan and O. Reilly, can be examined online.

1. Critical thinking skills (essay, review)
2. Problem resolution (through video conferencing)
3. Creativity (video project, portfolio)
4. Interaction (discussion, role-playing games)
5. Collaboration and group work (email, listserv, debate, conference discussions)
6. Knowledge demonstration (multiple choice task, true/false work, short answer exam, matching task)
7. Self-administration (journal, biography, portfolio, and so forth) (K.F. Hew, Sh. Liu, 2004).

There is an association between instruction and assessment. Building a quality assessment framework requires starting with a foundation that emphasizes the process of education and gives students plenty of chances to show what they have learned (2). A well-designed performance-based task that requires learners to exhibit academic capabilities along with studying in a variety of ways is essential to effective assessment. Performance levels are then determined by using

performance scales or rubrics that highlight significant accomplishment components and various achievement levels.

According to some researchers the primary objectives of successful educational assessments are to give students constructive criticism, encourage discussion about their work, and allow them to complete the task without constantly worrying about their mark. Furthermore, they can:

- Offer immediate feedback, enabling customization and modification.
- Foster a relationship with students by communicating with them and showing them that their teachers genuinely worry about their education.
- Enhance learning and performance by involving learners and allowing them to assume ownership of their education.

The most effective tool available to teachers for delving deeper into their students' knowledge, needs, and progress toward mastering the necessary content and skills is an excellent in quality classroom assessment.

Furthermore, the assessment as empowerment and learning approach views evaluation assignments as the centerpiece of an entire range of variables that define the broader assessment process. Since this will largely determine the self-regulation of learners and therefore, their integration of learning beyond initial tasks, decisions will be made regarding significant elements including learner involvement with the process of assessment or how the data obtained from the assessment the procedure will be used when designing assessment tasks.

The process of quality assessment entails gathering data to support assessments of the caliber of learning attained by students. Assessments of students' work are based on data gathered over time from a variety and variety of tasks to guarantee they are justifiable and comparable.

It ought to demonstrate that pupils' present comprehension serves as a good foundation for their future education.

Skill-based evaluation ought to be a continuous procedure with progress tracking over time. It ought to be diverse in nature, offer multiple opportunities for pupils to exhibit the depth and scope of their knowledge, cover various topics and balance, guided by content descriptions and modes of assessment (such as multimodal presentations, written, spoken, and signed).

Strategies for assessment suitable for the assessment conditions (e.g., supervised, open) along with the educational area.

The study discovered that while evaluating the effectiveness and productivity of individual educational and professional growth providers is the primary goal of assessment, a more comprehensive evaluation of the institution in its entirety is as important. Developing an organization for learning of some kind that is in charge of more than just evaluating current providers is an established pattern in all the processes that this research looked at. These groups facilitate stakeholder contact and provide a direct connection between the system's core goals and professional development for education. This connection is referred to by corporate learning organizations as "becoming a strategic partner" within the company. This kind of organization acts as a conduit between suppliers and consumers, gathers data about workforce requirements and ongoing initiatives, and promotes communication among significant individuals.

We use the term evaluation to mean to the multistep process of assessing the productivity and quality of educational and professional growth activities, after the thorough study of the research on higher education assessment in Palomba and Banta (1999).

The phase in the assessment procedure where productivity and quality metrics are compared to a performance standard is called an evaluation. Furthermore, according to Epstein (1992), productivity refers to the quantity and caliber of services produced with a specific set of resources. It is equivalent to efficiency in this sense. The productivity of the education provider has increased if it can deliver the same amount of services in a better quality or quantity. Efficacy and quality are interchangeable terms. There is no universally accepted definition of quality; instead, it varies depending on the individual. The definition of quality usually becomes clear throughout the procedure of determining the assessment's objectives. The performance standards set by various stakeholders, such as employers, parents, accreditors, and students, including the state, influence the performance or quality of an educational system (McGuinness, 1997).

Regardless of the method used to evaluate providers, our analysis of the research and case studies revealed that there are essentially three steps involved, each with crucial prerequisites (for a thorough description of the evaluation procedure in higher education, refer to Palomba and Banta, 1993):

- ◆ Determine the objectives of professional or educational growth.
- ◆ Evaluate the performance: Determine and put into practice performance metrics.
- ◆ Assess the degree to which the professional development and education objectives are met by the performance indicators.

Result and Conclusion

In evaluations, the initial step-identifying goals-is frequently disregarded. Assessors risk committing to evaluating outcomes that are not directly related to the aims of the educational system when they jump straight into the second process, which is creating performance measures, without first identifying goals. They could create superfluous measurements or ignore measures that represent the main goals of the system. Time will be lost in the first place gathering and examining pointless data. In the second case, people won't be aware of if the system is accomplishing significant goals.

Four parameters are included in this framework to ensure the level of teaching performance:

- establishes and adheres to procedures for hiring employees and establishing terms of employment that are equitable, transparent, and understand the value of teaching;
- provides chances for and encourages teaching staff members' professional growth;
- promotes academic endeavors to fortify the connection between research and teaching;
- promotes the use of cutting-edge technology and innovative teaching strategies (Palomba and Banta, 1999).

Elken and Stensaker (2018) offer another viewpoint on improving quality; they include the idea of quality work, which adopts a focused-on-practice approach and focuses on the various actors, formal and informal processes, and ongoing shaping of daily practice to improve quality in higher education (Elken & Stensaker, 2018).

The assessment approach should, to the greatest degree feasible, maximize domain coverage for general, higher-order abilities, particularly with regard to valued skills. The evaluation should, in particular, have a "high ceiling" to prevent unnecessarily restricting measurable advances that exceed expectations. Similarly, disciplines with a widely accepted body of information and an attainable agreement regarding competence should be prioritized when it

comes to discipline-specific abilities. It will be necessary to use a variety of item types in both scenarios, including open-ended and constructed-response item variations. Keep in mind that the ability of expert systems to automatically assess certain answer forms has an impact on the validity/feasibility trade-off (Elken & Stensaker, 2018).

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